

IPBES AR BBA Chapter 2 – Snowball literature search for literature on business dependency on biodiversity (C)

Detailed categories of the review template for the literature review, including the name of the category (category), its description (description) and the possible answer categories (answer categories).

For the following categories—Business sector, Business size, Ecosystem type, Ecosystem services, Biodiversity indicators, and Dependency typology—existing typologies found in the literature were used as response options (source of the classification in parentheses).

Information category	Description	Answer categories
Id	Unique id given to each reference	
Doi	Unique DOI address to each reference	
Reviewer	Name of the reviewer (anonymized)	Open answer
Inclusion/Exclusion	Include the reference in literature review or not	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include - Exclude
Reason to exclude	Reason to exclude	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inaccessible paper - Assess impacts rather than dependencies - Study based on scenarios or essays that do not produce new empirical evidence - Not business-related paper - Conceptual paper - Review, meta-analysis
Publication outlet	For example, journal name, working paper series, white paper organization, technical	Open answer

Information category	Description	Answer categories
	report group etc.	
Research gap	A knowledge gap, the reference seeks to address	Open answer
Research aim	Objective of the study	Open answer
Country	Country where the study was carried out	Open answer
Business sector (United Nations, 2008).	Business sector covered by the study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sector as per ISIC categories: - Agriculture, forestry and fishing - Mining and quarrying - Manufacturing - Electricity, gas steam and air conditioning supply - Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation - Construction - Wholesale and retail trade - Transportation and storage - Accommodation and food service - Information and communication - Financial and insurance - Real estate - Professional, scientific and technical - Administrative and support service - Public administration and defence, compulsory social security - Education

Information category	Description	Answer categories
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human health and social work - Arts, entertainment and recreation - Other service - Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods and services for households - Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies - Multiple - Unsure
<p>Business size</p> <p>Categories used in the Chapter 1 —Setting the Scene— of this assessment</p>	<p>Size of the business studied</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Micro: <5 participants - Small: 5-50 participants - Medium: 51-500 participants - Large: >500 participants
<p>Ecosystem type (IPBES,)</p>	<p>Type of ecosystem studied</p>	<p>Categories used in previous IPBES assessment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tropical dry and humid forests - Mountain systems - Grassland and savanna - Insular and linear coastal areas - Temperal and boreal forests - Tundra - Drylands - Wetland and freshwater systems - Linear coastal areas - Urban and semi-urban - Agricultural/silvicultural/aquacultural/other Other/multiple - Not specified
<p>If other/multiple ecosystem type, please specify which</p>		<p>Open answer</p>

Information category	Description	Answer categories
Ecosystem service (IPBES, 2019)	Ecosystem services studied	<p>Categories as in the typology of ecosystem services in the IPBES Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services (2019):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat creation and maintenance - Pollination and dispersal of seeds - Regulation of air quality - Regulation of climate - Regulation of ocean acidification - Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing - Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality - Formation, protection and decontamination of soils - Regulation of hazards and extreme events - Regulation of organisms detrimental to humans" - Energy - Food and feed - Materials and assistance - Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources - Learning and inspiration - Physical and psychological experiences - Supporting identities - Maintenance of options - Other - Not specified - Multiple
If other or multiple ES, please specify which		Open answer
Dependency typology (ENCORE, n d.)	Type of dependency studied	<p>Categories following the ENCORE typology (https://encorenature.org/en/explore):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct physical input: ecosystem services that are direct physical input into a production process

Information category	Description	Answer categories
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enables Production Process: ecosystem services that are an enabling factor for all or part of a production process - Mitigate Direct Impacts: ecosystem services that help to mitigate direct impacts associated with a production process - Protection from Disruption: ecosystem services that provide protection from disruption to the production process - Other
	<p>Biodiversity indicator used in the study if any (IPBES, 2018)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individual organisms - Biophysical assemblages (communities, ecosystems, biomes, populations, Gaia, Pachamama, ...) - Biophysical processes (evolutions, functions, ecosystem processes, ecological resilience) - Biodiversity (genetic, functional, phylogeny diversity, uniqueness) - None
Quantitative/qualitative	Quantitative or qualitative methods used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quantitative - Qualitative - Both methods used
If qualitative: Narrative	If qualitative study, narrative of the main results	Open answer
If quantitative: Magnitude of a dependency	If quantitative study, magnitude of the dependency	Open answer
If quantitative: Unit of measurement	If quantitative study, unit of the measurement	Open answer

Information category	Description	Answer categories
Primary method used	Primary method used in the study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monetary valuation - Socio-cultural and participatory method - Life Cycle Assessment Methods - Biophysical and Ecological Measurement - Scenario analysis - Integrated Multicriteria Methods - Others
Other methods used	Other methods used	Open answer
Primary or secondary data	Type of data used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary - Secondary - Both
Source of data/reference	Source of data	Open answer
Spatial scale of analysis	On which spatial scale was the business dependencies studied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local - National - Regional - Global
Other methods used	Extent of the business studied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local - National - International - Unsure
Spatial dependencies	Did the reference study spatial dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, related to physical flows, e.g. water - Yes, related to supply chains & trade from elsewhere - Yes, related to movement of species - Yes, through multiple/other. - No

Information category	Description	Answer categories
If multiple spatial dependencies, please write which		Open answer
Temporal dependencies	Did the reference study temporal dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No - Yes, seasonality - Yes, storage - Yes, both - Yes, other
If other temporal dependencies, please specify		Open answer
Synergies	Did the reference study synergies between dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No - Synergy within business - Synergy among business/sectors - Synergies within and among business/sectors - Synergy between business and other societal goals - Synergies that enhance bd and climate change - Outcomes - Yes, other
Trade-offs	Did the reference study trade-offs between dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No - Trade-off within business - Trade-off with other business - Trade-off with flow of NCPs to civil society and IPLs - Trade off with business and other NCPs, BD - Yes, other
Indigenous people's dependencies	Did the reference study indigenous people's dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No - Unsure

Information category	Description	Answer categories
	on biodiversity	

References

ENCORE. (n.d.). Explore natural capital risks and opportunities. ENCORE. <https://encorenature.org/en/explore>

IPBES. (2018). *The IPBES regional assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services for Europe and Central Asia*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3237429>

IPBES (2019), *Global assessment report of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*, Brondízio, E. S., Settele, J., Díaz, S., Ngo, H. T. (eds). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. 1144 pages. ISBN: 978-3-947851-20-1

IPBES (2022). *Methodological assessment of the diverse values and valuation of nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7687931>

United Nations, 2008. *International Standard Industrial Classification of all All-Economic Activities (ISIC), Rev.4*. Statistical Papers. Series M. No.4/Rev.4) <https://doi.org/10.18356/8722852c-en>